

WORKSHOP REPORT

1. Basic Information

Venue:

Date:

Total number of participants:

Invited Experts (Affiliation, Position, Gender, as well as Name if consent is given):

2. Topic of the Workshop

Which work package(s) did you discuss?

- WP 1 - Local responsibilities and services
- WP 2 - Local financial arrangements
- WP 3 - Structure of local government
- WP 4 - Intergovernmental relations of local governments
- WP 5 - People's participation in local decision-making

Which practices did you discuss and evaluate?

What other practices did the workshop participants suggest to include in your country dossier regarding the work package(s) discussed?

3. Outcome of the Workshop

How did the workshop participants evaluate the local government practices collected so far in your country dossier regarding the work package(s) discussed. Please also take into account the following guiding questions. **500-600 words**

- What are the (explicit or implicit) objectives of the practice, especially concerning urban local governments, on the one hand, and rural local governments, on the other? Do the practices achieve these objectives?
- The practice described does not necessarily have to be a best or good practice. What are the factors of success or failure? Do these factors differ in urban and rural settings?

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